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THE PLACE OF PIANO ART IN UZBEKISTAN

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***Abstract.** The art of piano playing, which is a significant part of the Uzbek national music culture, has been developing in our country for centuries. The legacy of these educators continues in the Piano Department at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, where faculty members and students actively contribute to the preservation and advancement of piano traditions.*

***Keywords:** composer, piano, genre, sonata.*

The art of piano playing, which is a significant part of the Uzbek national music culture, has been developing in our country for centuries. The connection between instrumental music and the lives of people has existed since ancient times. Traditional folk melodies and compositions performed on various instruments have been preserved and adapted to piano performances, reaching us in modern interpretations.

By the 20th century, piano art gained prominence, evolving alongside the introduction of classical and academic music directions in the 1920s and 1930s. Initially, composers focused on creating solo pieces and small ensembles for the piano. Over time, the genre expanded to include sonatas, concertos, and complex works that greatly contributed to the development of Uzbek academic music and piano performance.

The establishment of the Tashkent State Conservatory in 1936 marked a turning point for the development of piano art in Uzbekistan. The presence of the piano department among its founding faculties paved the way for professional growth in the field. Teachers like S. Benyaminov, N. Hoshimov, and R. Yusupova, who were representatives of prestigious piano schools in St. Petersburg and Moscow, played a

crucial role in shaping the Uzbek piano tradition. Their expertise and dedication allowed young Uzbek pianists to achieve remarkable success on both national and international stages.

These teachers, who were not only accomplished performers but also theoreticians with a deep understanding of piano techniques, provided students with a comprehensive education. Their combined practical and theoretical methods ensured that students developed versatile skills and innovative approaches. Today, the legacy of these educators continues in the Piano Department at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, where faculty members and students actively contribute to the preservation and advancement of piano traditions.

Notable Uzbek pianists, such as People's Artists of Uzbekistan A. Radjabov and I. Djalilov, along with Honored Artists and competition laureates, represent the success of this institution. Their achievements demonstrate the strength of Uzbek piano education and its influence on the global music scene. Moreover, students and alumni regularly participate in national and international competitions, festivals, and concerts, further showcasing Uzbekistan's rich piano heritage.

Recognizing the importance of piano art, Uzbekistan has implemented numerous initiatives to support young talent. The "Spring of Youth" piano competition is one such example, providing a platform for emerging pianists to showcase their skills and achieve recognition. In 2021, President Sh. Mirziyoyev established a "Boarding School Specialized in Piano Art" in Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, reflecting a commitment to nurturing the next generation of pianists.

The government has also introduced policies to promote the further development of piano art. On December 27, 2021, the President signed a resolution aimed at enhancing the infrastructure and opportunities for piano education and performance. This decision underscores the nation's dedication to elevating the cultural and aesthetic standards of its people through music.

The cultural policies of Uzbekistan further affirm the importance of piano art in society. Large-scale festivals, such as the "Melodies of the East" music festival, include a focus on piano performances, allowing for cultural exchange and the celebration of

piano artistry. The establishment of specialized schools, like the Boarding School for Piano Art in Nukus, ensures the preservation of this art form for future generations. These schools focus not only on performance but also on theory, composition, and musicology, providing students with a comprehensive education in piano art.

Technological advancements have also played a role in the evolution of piano art in Uzbekistan. Digital platforms and online masterclasses enable students to learn from international experts, while modern recording studios allow pianists to produce high-quality recordings of Uzbek compositions. These recordings are instrumental in introducing Uzbek piano music to global audiences, further strengthening the nation's cultural presence.

In our free and prosperous land, it is essential for every young person, regardless of their chosen profession, to understand and appreciate the art of music. Piano art, with its ability to convey deep emotions and complex ideas, serves as a means of enriching the human spirit and fostering creativity. In recent years, Uzbek and world classical piano works have gained renewed attention, with new interpretations and performances on prominent stages, including the Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater.

The growing recognition of piano art in Uzbekistan signals a bright future for this field. There is great hope for new creative achievements, the emergence of talented pianists, and the development of exceptional piano compositions. This ongoing progress promises to elevate Uzbekistan's cultural heritage and solidify its place in the global music community.

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